

Annual Report 2020

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This year we decided to ask a local artist, Clémence Mérouze, to create unique illustrations for the annual report. It is our way of showing support for the arts sector during the COVID-19 crisis.

Foreword

Year 2020 – The year of data

2020 started off as busy as usual for the CESSDA community, which was occupied with developing and providing data services as well as preparing for training events and meetings. As we all know, it soon turned into something none of us had ever seen. Now a year later, even though the global pandemic is still ongoing, it is possible to look back at what we have accomplished and what we have learned despite the surreal experience.

In early March, all face-to-face events were cancelled and transferred to webinar formats. Luckily, the CESSDA community was familiar with arranging virtual meetings and the move to home office happened swiftly without any major

disruptions. We have all taken a leap into a virtual culture that was not necessarily a prime factor in our everyday work lives. Meeting software improved drastically and new platforms were developed.

If life in a virtual world became a major trend in 2020, so did data. The demand for information on the virus from the natural and medical sciences exploded. In the case of a virus transmitted via human interaction, it was soon obvious that data about people, what they think and how they behave, would be of the utmost importance. To curtail the pandemic, we need to understand how societies tick, we need data on social phenomena.

In the beginning, the CESSDA data archives did not have many datasets concerning COVID-19, as we mainly depend on what researchers deposit. However, there were for example data on pandemics, infectious diseases, trust in government, health care, and such. It was also important to keep reminding the research community that even though there was a feeling of rush and urgency, the data should be collected properly so that it can be legally deposited and shared.

Many CESSDA Service Providers were supporting researchers, and some were even themselves involved in gathering new data on reactions to COVID-19 and on the measures to tackle it. CESSDA ERIC published an information webpage,

Foreword – Chair

highlighting both relevant data in the CESSDA Data Catalogue as well as Service Providers' initiatives and data sets. The Director of CESSDA initiated an Ambassadorship to deal with information requests in June 2020. The main task of the Ambassador is to serve as a contact point for Service Providers and outsiders approaching CESSDA for cooperation or support in COVID-19-related data services. I was invited to take up this mission.

Early on, COVID-19 and corona were added to the controlled multilingual vocabulary (CESSDA Vocabularies). When writing this in May 2021, there are over 150 study descriptions in English tagged with "COVID-19" or "corona" in the catalogue and the number keeps increasing. In autumn 2020, an interview series was started on COVID-19-related matters.

All in all, the pandemic did not cause CESSDA or its Service Providers to shut down. To the contrary, our users have had time to search and study existing data sources, while collecting data using traditional methods has been a challenge. As the CESSDA community was already working in a highly digitised environment and is a network of experts in data FAIRness, the demand for data that the pandemic instigated was reflected in an increased demand for CESSDA services. Despite this success, nobody can be satisfied with the current situation. It is a global tragedy in many ways and it continued to limit CESSDA's

operations as well. We are eager to meet old and new colleagues as well as our users in person. Long-term social distancing is not an ideal state of being. After all, CESSDA is a community, often referred to as the "CESSDA family".

I am writing this foreword as Chair of the General Assembly (GA) of CESSDA. I was elected as Chair alongside the Austrian representative Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy, as Vice Chair, at our meeting in November. That also happened remotely. We were both GA representatives before the pandemic and most of the representatives have met us several times.

Our team will be proud to Chair the GA of CESSDA ERIC for the two-year period 2021–2022. Even though virtual meetings are less time consuming, we hope that not all meetings will be held remotely after the pandemic. I am very much looking forward to actually meeting people again and being able to have good, face-to-face conversations.

Helena Laaksonen
Chair of the General Assembly

Foreword – Director

On 9 March 2020, a CESSDA delegation landed at Zagreb Airport to attend the European Presidency Conference in Rijeka. In the taxi we were informed that the conference had been cancelled due to COVID-19. We decided to continue our trip, as flying back immediately would have been more expensive, and instead try set up an alternative programme – which worked.

Since then, there have not been any business trips. They have been replaced with Zoom, Microsoft Teams, WebEx, and Skype and staff moved to home

offices. SSHOC project consortium meetings, EOSC Executive Board, General Assembly, Service Providers' Forum, new projects' acquisition – everything went virtual.

As the CESSDA community grew, we shifted our focus to improving our communication with existing members. On tools and services, we stabilised as well. Instead of developing new tools, we focused on the sustainability of existing core tools. We organised targeted webinars on the CESSDA Data Catalogue and the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide.

CESSDA Main Office decided to move from the old villa at Parkveien to a single floor office at Solheimsgaten, still in the centre of Bergen and in a livelier business area. Our internal communication is improved by working on the same floor and the office space is significantly cheaper. As we approach 2022, there is a desire to go back to what we deem to be normal. In the last few months, we have been able to come back to the office several days a week to have face-to-face meetings. We have adapted well to online meetings, which can be very efficient. However, we are social beings and we also need to connect in person. Let's hope this continues! Zoom is fine but meeting each other is better.

Ron Dekker
Director

Highlights

COVID-19

It is not exactly a highlight, but we responded to the COVID-19 pandemic. Helena Laaksonen from Finland was appointed as COVID-19 ambassador to have a single point of contact, and several Service Providers set up information on COVID-19 data; the CESSDA website set up a special COVID-19 page as well, providing information and links to the national pages. CESSDA also updated its thesaurus as COVID-19, "infectious diseases", etc. were not available for filtering or searching in the metadata. We also did an interview series and campaigns on social media. And we got involved in COVID-19 projects, collaborating with the life sciences.

CESSDA Platform updates

We saw the beginning of a shift from developing technology to operating services.

With the Technical Working Group finalising the foundations of the Cloud Platform and Technical Guidelines, a new model of operating CESSDA services was developed. The focus shifted towards continued maintenance of the existing technology and establishing and disseminating our technical standards.

In addition, the service aspect of delivering value and support to our users was strengthened. As a result, CESSDA is ready to provide professional services in the EOSC landscape.

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and European projects

CESSDA was a member of the EOSC Executive Board that prepared the foundation of the EOSC Association. CESSDA also (in 2021) became a member of the association, continuing its commitment to EOSC via membership of task forces and participating in EOSC-related projects.

CESSDA is the coordinator of the SSHOC project and there were regular meetings with the other cluster coordinators. This resulted in joint position papers on open science and EOSC.

Main impacts from EU projects & internal projects in 2020

In 2020 we changed the procedure for CESSDA projects from "open calls" to a CESSDA Agenda 21-22. We invited our Service Providers to work on designated tools and provide services.

Agenda 21-22 / Roadmaps

CESSDA decided in 2020 that there was a need for change in the way the organisation strives to achieve its goals. The Agenda 21-24 is a multiannual, concrete work plan that serves as a basis for CESSDA internal projects during that period. It guides Service Providers towards delivering products and services that align with the Consolidated Roadmap and the CESSDA Strategy.

Introduction

Introduction

CESSDA provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data archives across Europe, with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation.

Each member assigns a national data service that takes care of data curation and data

services. These CESSDA Service Providers act as trusted repositories and demonstrate their reliability to researchers as well as national and international research funders.

The consortium welcomed Ireland and Iceland as new members – and with Italy joining in 2021, the CESSDA consortium now consists of 22 members and 1 observer.

**Activities and
Results**

Strategic level activities

The increasing number of requirements by the European Commission (EC), EOSC, ESFRI, and fellow ERICs has shown that CESSDA cannot afford to remain solely focused on internal developments. This was made apparent through the coordination of one of the EOSC thematic cluster projects and chairing the ERIC Forum.

CESSDA is a member of the EOSC Executive Board, has an advisory role in the EOSC Hub and OpenAIRE projects. Furthermore, CESSDA has engaged with the EC and ESFRI on issues such as sustainability and future funding models for Research Infrastructures.

CESSDA therefore moved from a bottom-up approach to commissioning work closely related to its strategic goals.

Outlook 2021-2024

CESSDA decided in 2020 that there was a need for change in the way the organisation strives to achieve its goals. Priorities were set together with appropriate policies, procedures and processes to support further developments and strategic planning in the upcoming 2021–2024 period.

The Agenda 21-24 is a multiannual, concrete work plan that serves as a basis for CESSDA internal projects in the period of 2021-2024. The agenda guides CESSDA Service Providers towards delivering products and services that align with the Consolidated Roadmap and the CESSDA Strategy. It remains flexible enough for each team of Service Providers to create the final proposals which will engage partners that have the knowledge, expertise, and capacity to deliver required outputs. The Agenda 21-24 will kick-off in January 2021.

In line with this, CESSDA also developed a new concept to update the roadmaps for each CESSDA pillar. The Consolidated Roadmap is a document that combines updated roadmaps for all four CESSDA pillars. It is a thematic pathway to delivering the CESSDA Strategy and vision. The revised document has a medium-term perspective and provides updates and sets priorities for the CESSDA Strategy 2018–2022 and beyond.

All CESSDA Working Groups aligned their efforts to ensure the Consolidated Roadmap was cohesive and complementary. An additional novelty is the introduction of the Widening and Outreach pillar from 2021 onwards. It became a new strategic pillar with a set of activities in the coming years. It is also a horizontal pillar, building upon all other CESSDA Pillars (Trust, Training, and Tools).

CESSDA Training

- » raises awareness on open science and FAIR data principles
- » increases data skills of researchers and trainers
- » provides training and educational materials
- » builds internal capacity at the level of Service Providers and
- » ensures coordination with other European partners.

CESSDA Tools

- » provides tools for data curation and publication
- » supports finding, accessing and reusing research data and metadata
- » works according to FAIR principles and regardless of borders
- » is committed to respecting data privacy and security issues.

CESSDA Trust

- » aims for a consortium of trusted repositories with full European coverage
- » supports Service Providers and partners at different levels of maturity
- » shares expertise
- » enables the scaling of services while minimising duplication of effort.

As technology and services are defragmented and consolidated, trust between organisational partners is increasingly important. Human factors remain critical and the CESSDA mission ensures the availability of data experts capable of ensuring trust in data assets for the long term.

Widening and Outreach

CESSDA is developing a Pan-European collaboration going beyond the current CESSDA membership. It does this by addressing data archives in services in the social sciences and humanities in prospective non-member countries. CESSDA wishes to grow, while also strengthening ties with current members. It wants to be a leader in European data discovery and actively represent Europe on the global stage of data driven social science research. CESSDA will increase its visibility, share standards, and encourage the uptake of its tools and policies in scientific research communities. This pillar will actively collaborate with the other CESSDA pillars.

Activities and results

Development of KPIs

It was necessary for the European Commission as well as member and associated countries to evaluate their participation in international organisations. ESFRI was asked to advise on the monitoring of research infrastructures and develop a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). CESSDA was given over a year to prepare and respond adequately to ongoing discussions at the European level.

CESSDA started developing its own KPIs in late 2019. During 2020, a number of activities were undertaken such as consultations with Service

Providers and a pilot collection of possible KPIs. In late 2020 the final list of KPIs was approved by the CESSDA General Assembly.

The list of KPIs to be finalised in 2021 will offer members and the EC the opportunity to provide efficiency in progress monitoring for the Consortium. The selection and definitions of indicators, such as the exact requirements from ESFRI and the use of the information will evolve over time. In addition, standardisation and comparability of metrics will be addressed periodically.

Activities and results

Operational level activities

Working Group summaries

Technical Working Group

The Technical Working Group is made up of representatives from ten Service Providers and members of the Main Office technical team. During 2020, the group had regular monthly meetings and undertook a wide range of activities: reviews of technical policy documents, the performance of the technical infrastructure, and CESSDA's tools and services.

[CESSDA Technical Guidelines](#) were improved. If any performance issues were highlighted, they were discussed, corrected, and actions were proposed. Other activities took place such as monitoring of the platform, core products, good technical practice within the Service Provider community, discussions about relevant conferences, workshops, and training courses to attend.

Progress updates were carefully monitored regarding the development and maintenance of the Data Catalogue, Metadata Validator, Question Bank, ELSST Thesaurus and Vocabularies Service. Additionally, new processes and procedures relating to the CESSDA Technical Infrastructure were promoted in relevant channels.

Training Working Group

The main aim of the CESSDA Training Working Group (Training WG) is to review and guide CESSDA related activities, and work together with other training communities. Due to the pandemic, the original plan for 2020 had to be changed and face-to-face events could not take place as intended. Several events were moved online while others were postponed to 2021. Outputs and results from training and widening projects in 2019 were embedded on the training web page and published in the CESSDA Zenodo community. Recordings were published on the CESSDA Training YouTube channel and further promoted via social media.

The Training WG worked closely with projects on widening and new data types. It also offered support for online events for CESSDA Service Providers and other CESSDA projects and initiatives (eight online events in 2020), as well as the publication of outputs to Zenodo. The Training and Widening WGs collaborated with the Main Office on the CESSDA Publication Policy & Procedures document.

Tools and Services Working Group

The Tools and Services Working Group (WG) consisted of five members: FSD, EKKE, GESIS, TARKI and DNA. In 2020, the WG worked closely with the Technical WG and the CESSDA Chief Technical Officer in prioritising and advising on the development of CESSDA's tools and services.

Activities and results

The main goals in 2020 were to upskill Service Providers in metadata creation according to the CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM). This is of use for both existing and forthcoming services. Aspects considered included advanced human and machine-actionable discovery, supporting the Tools and Services Platform approach, and working with Service Providers and the external community.

In 2020, the Working Group reviewed CESSDA's policy documents, held regular meetings, and monitored and evaluated Work Plan Tasks under the Tools and Services Pillar, including the CESSDA Metadata Office. Other tools and services which were further developed in 2020 included ELSST, CVS and CDC, CESSDA Ontology Management System, New Data Types, and the EuroQuestionBank.

2020 also saw advances in clarifying the roles and responsibilities of the WG. This included considerations such as the selection of members, the funding model, enhancement and clarification of the Work Plan process, and refinement of the roadmap and its management.

Trust Working Group

The main objective of the CESSDA Trust Working Group was to manage and maintain CESSDA Trust Pillar activities. The Working Group met regularly while WG Leaders also actively participated in CESSDA Working Group Leader activities.

During this period, the Trust Support Work Plan and CESSDA Development Model (CDM) were under the Trust pillar. Activities were designed to address a number of aspects of the CESSDA Strategic Plan including Service Providers acting as trusted repositories for Governments, Research Funders including the EC, and researchers' trust in Service Providers. The activity plan followed the Trust Roadmap objectives, which were broadly delivered. The Trust WG supported the development of CESSDA's Agenda 21-24 proposals and made recommendations for updates to the CESSDA Strategy. These were conveyed as CESSDA revised its processes and procedures to define, monitor, report, and review activities. The activities of the Trust Working Group and other Trust Activities were separated, as prescribed by the revised approach to WGs and CESSDA pillars.

Work Plan 2020 summaries

Cloud Platform 2018-2020

The aim of the Cloud Platform task was to lead the design, realisation, and operationalisation of the CESSDA Research Infrastructure on the Google Cloud Platform. The intention throughout was to support CESSDA's strategic goals.

The major outputs were:

- » Observability – metrics and logs were constantly collected and automatic notifications are sent for several products and tools when pre-set thresholds were exceeded.
- » Quality Assurance – the existing Technical Architecture and Software Maturity Level documents were revised and added to the CESSDA Technical Guidelines as the major sections [Technical Infrastructure](#) and [Software Maturity Levels](#) respectively.
- » Increasing the external visibility of the platform – two articles were published via LinkedIn: [Documentation As Code](#) and [Deploying microservices with Helm](#); presentations were made on “CESSDA Product Quality: Theory and Practice” and “Documentation as code” at the EURISE Expert online meetings; presentations and training proposals submitted to various conferences which were subsequently cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic .
- » Creating more “how to” documentation –

extensive revisions to and restructuring of the [CESSDA Technical Guidelines](#) which culminated in a new release on 01/12/2020.

- » Expanding external connectivity – options for an Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure were explored, the solution offered by EduTeams was trailed. Managed Application Programming Interfaces for CESSDA's core products (where relevant) were exposed and documented in a standard manner, and automated testing of them was introduced.
- » Documenting lessons learned, achievements and future work. This has been done via an internal report, and the suggestions for future work will feed into the planning processes for 2021-22.

Training Activities 2020

The CESSDA Training Activities task was led by GESIS (DE) in 2020, while ADP (SI), AUSSDA (AT), CSDA (CZ), DANS (NL), DNA (DK), DCS – IEN (RS), EKKE (EL), FORS (CH), NSD (NO), SND (SE), UKDS (UK) contributed as project partners.

A beta version of the Data Archiving Guide (DAG) was delivered. The DAG website will be designed to provide employees at social science data archives with a general understanding of the work performed by a data archive. The DAG focused on common ground and will be a useful tool for professionals new to data archiving or those who are knowledgeable in one domain and seeking to broaden their expertise.

Activities and results

Two guides were created: a Handbook on Creating Videos for CESSDA and a Step-by-step Guide on “How to prepare and deliver a webinar”, as well as a video to promote both guides. These guides build capacity across all Service Providers to produce their own reusable videos for training and promotion, as well as organise webinars following CESSDA’s procedures and using its software.

Two webinars were held: A Data Discovery Webinar on Harmonised Data for Comparative Research and an online event on the processing of personal data for research, including compliance with GDPR. The first webinar was part of a series on data discovery. It addressed Harmonised Data for Comparative Research and included presentations on sources of harmonised data as well as approaches and tools for harmonising data sources for cross-national research. The second webinar was a presentation of the GDPR related to the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG), specifically to the chapters Process and Protect, emphasizing the importance of planning ahead to ensure compliance with the legal requirements of the GDPR.

Lastly, The CESSDA Train-the-Trainer Package (TTT) was updated. A revision of TTT was necessary in order to align the content with the latest version of the DMEG. Namely, 43 documents from the Train-the-Trainer materials have been revised.

The task also supported CESSDA’s promotion of CESSDA Training activities via Twitter. There were more than 180 Tweets concerning CESSDA Training activities in 2020. Training materials were added to the website and relevant platforms.

European Question Bank 2020

The task on the European Question Bank (EQB) was led by GESIS (DE) and supported by MK DASS (MK) in 2020.

The goal was to develop a functioning web application with technical improvements and with the inclusion of question-/study-level metadata from several CESSDA Service Providers.

The main achievements of the task were:

- » A search application with over 10,000 questions and related metadata that meet user requirements.
- » A usability test provided insights into how the user interface and user experience could be improved.
- » Improvements on the EQB harvester which affect how the content of Service Providers (SND, GESIS, NSD, CenterData/ DANS) is harvested, imported, indexed and displayed in the EQB User Interface.
- » Implementation of the DDI Converter to convert DDI Codebook documentation into DDI Lifecycle CMM 3.2.

Activities and results

- » With the CESSDA Seed funding, it was possible to support MK DASS with their metadata documentation on several surveys and question items using the GESIS Questionnaire Editor.
- » Presentation of the EQB task, user interface and requirements at the EDDI 2020 conference.

New Data Types 2020

This task had two main goals. The first was to provide researchers and archival staff with guidance on working with new data types. Particularly digital trace data with regard to ethical questions such as related to informed consent, issues of documentation, archiving, and linking (with survey data). Secondly, to increase the visibility of CESSDA as a hub of expertise on new data types.

The task was led by GESIS (DE), and ADP (SI), CSDA (CZ), EKKE/SoDaNet (EL), SASD (SK) and TARKI (HU) contributed as partners. The NDT task achieved these goals through webinars and online workshops, and publications. Both of these offerings were aimed at researchers as well as archivists working, or intending to work, with new data types. The focus of the NDT task was on digital trace data, especially social media data.

One of the webinars covered the topic of “Archiving Social Media Data: Challenges and Proposed Solutions” and featured presentations by experts from CESSDA Service Providers,

as well as other institutions (University of Edinburgh, Qualitative Data Repository of the Syracuse University, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research). Speakers shared their expertise regarding legal, ethical, and practical questions related to archiving social media data with 142 participants from all over the world. The slides from the presentations as well as a recording of the event were published on Zenodo and YouTube and have been viewed and downloaded more than 200 times.

Another outcome to highlight from the NDT task is the paper “Informed consent for linking survey and social media data – Differences between platforms and data types”. The paper was published in the IASSIST Quarterly journal. The paper provided guidance on informed consent for linking survey and social media data. This included specific suggestions for the wording of informed consent for data from different social media platforms. The paper also highlighted some of the work on social media data that CESSDA Service Providers had been involved in.

A [Guide on linking surveys and digital trace data](#) and a [Guide on archiving social media data](#) were also published under open access rules. The experiences from the NDT task showed that there was great interest in new data and the outputs the task produced can serve as helpful starting points or guidance for researchers and archivists who are working, or intend to work, with social media or digital trace data.

Activities and results

CESSDA Controlled Vocabulary Manager

The [CESSDA Vocabulary Service](#) provides a user-friendly source of standardised control vocabularies. This enables users to search, browse, and download controlled vocabularies in a variety of languages. The majority of the source (English) vocabularies included in the service have been created by the DDI Alliance. Translations of the DDI vocabularies have been provided by CESSDA members and associated organisations. The service also contains an editor, where authorised users create, manage and translate the vocabularies. Users can search, browse and download the controlled vocabularies in different formats in the user interface. The vocabularies help Service Providers to harmonise metadata across organisations, thus facilitating data discovery for researchers.

Participants of the task in 2020 were FSD (FI), and UKDS (UK) as content task leads, GESIS (DE) as main developer and technical task lead. The goal was to maintain and further develop a functioning web application with technical improvements and introduce new content. The main work was a complete rewrite of the version one CV Manager tool to replace the technology stack. The reasons behind this were the end of long-term support of the frontend framework as well as code quality and testability. A complete reimplemention of the CESSDA CV Manager was achieved along

with the compliance with the CESSDA Software Quality Standards regarding code quality and test coverage.

A number of changes were made to the content in 2020:

- » 3 new source language (English) vocabularies were published
- » 10 source language vocabularies previously published elsewhere were published in the CVS
- » 11 new translations (target language vocabularies) were published
- » 6 updates to existing source language vocabularies were published
- » 17 updates to existing translations were published.

In addition to the DDI Alliance and CESSDA, each Service Provider is now able to become an agency to maintain their own controlled vocabularies and include these via an open API into the study documentation workflows.

Activities and results

Trust activities 2020

As part of their commitment to CESSDA, all Service Providers work towards the internationally recognised CoreTrustSeal, a standard for acquiring the trustworthy digital repository (TDR) status. CoreTrustSeal is the recommended certification approach for data repositories within EOSC and is seen as important for enabling FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data. These developments reflect well on CESSDA's early selection of and support for "core" TDR standards. The Trust Activities task was led in 2020 by UKDS (UK), and DANS (NL), FSD (FI), GESIS (DE), ADP (SI) and SND (SE) contributed as project partners.

By the end of 2020, more than half of 22 Service Providers were certified and in the renewal cycle with all but the most recent CESSDA members. They were however actively involved in developing applications with the support of CESSDA and other trust-related projects. The team's publication "[Overview of Support Approaches](#)" provided input into a number of other CoreTrustSeal support activities.

The task members have a variety of roles in related trust activities including the CoreTrustSeal, Nestor Seal (DIN31644), RDA Repository Certification Interest Group and trustworthy digital repository support on the SSHOC, EOSC Nordic and FAIRsFAIR

projects. This allows the group members to maintain a wide knowledge of ongoing trust, FAIR and EOSC landscape issues and to feed this into ongoing CESSDA trust work. 2020 saw the release of a landscape overview report that leveraged the involvement in a range of trust activities elsewhere to provide relevant contextual information related to trust, CoreTrustSeal, as well as FAIR and open data. The report begins with a focus on the CoreTrustSeal as a Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR) standard for social sciences and humanities and then addresses an EOSC perspective and going beyond Europe.

The final area of work during 2020 was to review the content and interpretation of the CESSDA Annex II obligations, that define the responsibilities of all Service Providers. The Trust Group held a review meeting with CESSDA Main Office and the outcomes were presented at the trust workshop and at a meeting of the Service Provider Forum, after which a draft report was shared with all Service Providers for comments. This work provides an important perspective that will inform future work about aligning CESSDA member information across their obligations, the CoreTrustSeal, and emerging key performance indicators.

Activities and results

Metadata Office

The CESSDA Metadata Office (MDO) was established in 2019, to provide a core conceptual and strategic group to maintain and manage the CESSDA core metadata model and controlled vocabularies, and to provide a “metadata watch”. This work continued in 2020 and was split into two tasks. Task 1 managed the core metadata model, while task 2 managed the content and work for three key CESSDA controlled vocabulary services. The aim of the latter was to prepare them for their move to a service-based management structure from 2021.

Metadata Office Task 1

The CESSDA Service Providers who worked on task 1 were GESIS (DE) leading the task, supported by UKDS (UK), FSD (FI), and NSD (NO).

The MDO forms a conceptual and strategic group to maintain and manage CESSDA’s metadata-related material. It is the principal point of contact for metadata issues within CESSDA. The MDO stays up to date with the metadata requirements of CESSDA Service Providers and CESSDA projects, while simultaneously providing recommendations on metadata to CESSDA Service Providers.

In 2020, CESSDA increased its outreach to metadata players outside of CESSDA via newsletters, a webinar, a presentation at the

EDDI conference, a [report on metadata initiatives of interest to CESSDA and Service Providers](#) and an [article in IASSIST Quarterly](#). Furthermore, new versions of the CESSDA Metadata Model (CESSDA’s official metadata schema based on the DDI Lifecycle) and its User Guide were produced. MDO worked on DDI profiles for the schemas of the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) and the CESSDA EuroQuestionBank (EQB). This has been done to formalise the structure and facilitate the technical application of CESSDA’s metadata schemas.

The [DDI profiles for CDC](#), based on the DDI Codebook versions DDI2.5 and DDI 1.2.2, were published. The profiles furthermore support machine-actionable validation by the CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV). A great success of MDO task 1 work in 2020 was the creation of the CESSDA Metadata Validator. The CMV enables the validation of DDI documents against a given DDI profile. The primary goal was to improve metadata quality. The CMV is designed to validate any DDI file against any DDI profile. Therefore, it can be widely adopted for many use cases and is of great relevance, not just for the CESSDA community. Furthermore, work on a CMM UML Class diagram to represent the CMM is underway, and the first release for comments should be available in June 2021.

Metadata Office Task 2

The MDO task 2, led by UKDS (UK) and supported by FSD (FI), GESIS (DE) and NSD (NO), achieved its objectives for all three services.

The three assets covered in task 2 were:

- » the [European Language Social Science Thesaurus](#) (ELSST);
- » the [CESSDA Vocabulary Service](#) (CVS); and
- » the [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#) (CDC).

The annual updated content release for ELSST happened in June 2020. This was done to maintain its currency and relevance as a social science indexing service. Technical work was also undertaken to move ELSST to a new thesaurus management system and user interface, hosted on the CESSDA platform. The technical work was undertaken in the Ontology Management System task, while MDO task 2 covered ELSST content work to ensure there was no break in update continuity. The thesaurus will be managed by the ELSST content contact Service Provider from 2021.

A CVS user group was established, with Terms of Reference (TOR), updated content was added to the CVS, and testing of a system update was undertaken. The group will be managed by the CVS content contact Service Provider from 2021.

A CDC user group was established, with Terms of Reference; a controlled vocabulary (CV) for Service Provider was created; and the first stage of work was undertaken to establish a Data Access Interoperability CV for future catalogue filtering. In addition, metadata quality policy measures were created to provide a framework for future CDC improvement work. The group will be managed by the CDC content contact Service Provider from 2021.

CESSDA Ontology Management System

The CESSDA Ontology Management System task ran in 2020, alongside the Metadata Office (MDO) task 2 to facilitate technical work on the multilingual ELSST. MDO task 2 covered ELSST content work to ensure there was no break in currency update for ELSST as a key social science indexing service. Both tasks prepared ELSST for its move to a service-based management structure from 2021, at which point management will be undertaken by the ELSST Content contact Service Provider. The Work Plan Task was led by UKDS (UK) while FSD (FI) contributed as a project partner.

The task's objective was to upgrade the system in which ELSST is managed to [VocBench](#), a specialist open source ontology management system, and replace its user interface with the [Skosmos](#) open source browser. Both tools are

Activities and results

based on the [Simple Knowledge Organisation System](#) (SKOS), a W3C recommendation designed for the representation of thesauri and other structured controlled vocabularies to enable easy, open data linkage across

sources. Work on the move and upgrade of ELSST continued throughout the year, resulting in the successful release of the CESSDA ELSST platform in November 2020.

ELSST Thesaurus

Content language English

[Alphabetical](#) [Hierarchy](#)

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O
P Q R S T U V W Y Z

- ABILITY
- ABILITY ASSESSMENT → ABILITY EVALUATION
- ABILITY EVALUATION
- ABILITY GROUPING
- ABJURATION OF FAITH → RELIGIOUS EXPERIENCE
- ABORIGINAL PEOPLE → INDIGENOUS POPULATIONS
- ABORTION
- ABSENCE FROM SCHOOL → EDUCATIONAL ATTENDANCE
- ABSENCE FROM WORK → ABSENTEEISM (WORK)
- ABSENT PARENT → PARENTAL DEPRIVATION
- ABSENT PARENTS → PARENTAL DEPRIVATION
- ABSENTEEISM (WORK)
- ABUSE OF THE ELDERLY → ELDER ABUSE
- ABUSED CHILDREN → CHILD ABUSE
- ACADEMIC ABILITY
- ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT
- ACADEMIC ADMISSION → EDUCATIONAL ADMISSION
- ACADEMIC APTITUDE → ACADEMIC ABILITY
- ACADEMIC DEPARTMENTS
- ACADEMIC EVALUATION → EDUCATIONAL ASSESSMENT
- ACADEMIC FACILITIES → EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES
- ACADEMIC FREEDOM
- ACADEMIC GROUPING → EDUCATIONAL GROUPING
- ACADEMIC RECORDS → EDUCATIONAL RECORDS
- ACADEMIC SUCCESS → ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT
- ACADEMIC YEAR → EDUCATIONAL YEAR
- ACCENTS (DIALECT) → DIALECTS
- ACCESS TO COMPUTERS → ACCESS TO INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY
- ACCESS TO COUNTRYSIDE
- ACCESS TO EDUCATION
- ACCESS TO FACILITIES
- ACCESS TO HEALTH CARE → ACCESS TO HEALTH SERVICES
- ACCESS TO HEALTH SERVICES
- ACCESS TO ICT → ACCESS TO INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY
- ACCESS TO INFORMATION
- ACCESS TO INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY
- ACCESS TO INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY → ACCESS TO INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY
- ACCESS TO IT → ACCESS TO INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS TECHNOLOGY

Vocabulary information

TITLE	ELSST Thesaurus
DESCRIPTION	The European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) is a broad-based, multilingual thesaurus for the social sciences. It is owned and published by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) and its national Service Providers. The thesaurus consists of over 3,000 concepts and covers the core social science disciplines: politics, sociology, economics, education, law, crime, demography, health, employment, information and communication technology and, increasingly, environmental science.
PUBLISHER	CESSDA ERIC
LICENSE	Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
DATE ISSUED	2021-09-14
RIGHTS HOLDER	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) and its national Service Providers
TYPE	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme
URI	https://elsst.cessda.eu/id/

Resource counts by type

Type	Count
Concept	3341
• Deprecated concept	0

Term counts by language

Language	Preferred terms	Alternate terms	Hidden terms
Czech	3322	2008	0
Danish	3296	1778	0
German	3341	11146	0
Greek	3341	1993	0
English	3341	2642	0
Spanish	3253	830	0
Finnish	3341	3186	0
French	3341	2553	0
Lithuanian	3341	2874	0

Activities and results

Widening activities 2020

Widening activities in 2020 were built upon previous efforts and they were focused on ensuring the continuation of the selected important and successful activities. The activities were carried out by nine CESSDA Service Providers: CSDA (CZ, lead), GESIS (DE), FORS (CH), SND (SE), ADP (SI), TARKI (HU), CROSSDA (HR), MK DASS/ISPJR (MK) and DCS/IES (RS).

The CESSDA Mentorship Programme continued as regular support providing one-on-one guidance to CESSDA Partners and new or less mature member Service Providers. In 2020 the programme involved three mentors (ADP, FORS and SND) providing support to six mentees (CROSSDA (HR), CPC (XK), APIS (PT), RODA (RO), BAS (BG), and ISSDA (IE)).

In addition, a bi-weekly [CESSDA Newsletter for Data Service Professionals](#) was launched as a means of sharing information on Training Possibilities, Conferences and Events, Publications and Resources, Funding Opportunities and Collaborations, Employment Opportunities and News from the Community. The CESSDA Resource Directory (RD) was updated and upgraded in 2020 (RD 2.0 includes 244 resources). Since the launch in 2018, there have been significant content changes based on various tests and reviews and the structure of the RD became more user friendly. The RD is now available in the [Zotero library](#).

CESSDA Data Days in Poland initially prepared for April 2020 as a face-to-face meeting in Warsaw had to be first postponed and then moved to an online platform. [CESSDA Data Day 2021 – Social Science Data Archives in Poland: Opportunities for Researchers and Challenges Ahead](#), was organised on 18 March 2021 in cooperation with the [Polish Social Data Archive](#) (PADS) and [Qualitative Social Data Archive](#) (ADJ). The event was divided into two sessions, where the morning session was held in English. It included presentations by representatives of CESSDA, PADS, ADJ and ICM University of Warsaw and a panel session focused on Sharing Social Science Data in Poland. The afternoon workshop was held in Polish and covered data management.

The issue of transparency of analytical research published in scholarly journals has led to an increase in requirements for data accessibility. The need for a collective CESSDA response, a new activity on “Journals Outreach” was launched in 2020. Activities in 2020 aimed to assess journal requirements and needs, based on a secondary analysis and on interviews with journal editors. Service Provider capacities were also assessed, based on a survey and a follow-up focus group with selected CESSDA Service Providers. Recommendations were made for services to journals and a position statement and promotion strategy for collaboration with journals and publishers.

Activities and results

Strategic EC level activities

EOSC

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is high on the European Agenda. CESSDA actively participated in preparatory work including via EC projects and at the end of 2020, the EOSC Association was established. 2020 marked two years of preparations in the EOSC Executive Board, made up of three experts and eight European organisation representatives, of which CESSDA was one. CESSDA also participated in several EOSC Working Groups.

The Science Clusters (EOSC-Life, ENVRI FAIR, ESCAPE, PaNOSC, SSHOC) set up regular informal meetings and published joint position papers. In addition, the science clusters jointly prepared the large EOSC Future project to realise this EOSC in 2023.

European Union funded projects

Ongoing projects

SSHOC - Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud

Duration: 01.01.2019 – 30.04.2022, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) cluster project Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) continued its successful implementation in 2020. CESSDA is supported by several Service Providers in this project (NSD, UKDS, ADP, GESIS, SND, FSD, FORS, DNA, AUSSDA, DANS) and coordinates the work of 48 institutions, covering all SSH ESFRI Landmarks and Projects as well as relevant international SSH data infrastructures and associations. The SSHOC project aims to realise the transition

 cessda The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives contributes to the Digital Future of Europe via its partnership in the following projects.

European Research Infrastructures advancing the European Open Science Cloud

Social Scientific Communities advancing Social Scientific Research

EURHisFIRM

COORDINATE
COhort cOMmunity Research and Development Infrastructure Network for Access Throughout Europe

ERIC FORUM

European Research Infrastructures advancing the Digital Future of Europe

Activities and results

from the current landscape with disciplinary silos and separated e-infrastructure facilities into a cloud-based infrastructure where data are FAIR and tools and training are easily available.

The second year of the SSHOC project coincided with the global COVID-19 pandemic crisis. As an EC project including EU Research Infrastructures, SSHOC contributed to the global discussion about COVID-19 and actions towards creating the European data platform – COVID-19 Data portal, by providing its considerations to the European Commission. An article was also published to showcase the potential and importance of SSH contribution in addressing global challenges. This assisted in laying out the specific actions SSHOC has taken to continue serving their communities in the context of the corona crisis.

The SSHOC consortium expanded in 2020, welcoming three new beneficiaries representing EURHISFIRM, a Horizon 2020 project that aims to design a research infrastructure on historical and historic economic data. Identified links with EURHISFIRM added up to the existing European Value Studies and Migration Studies Pilots, which are already a part of the project.

Managing a project of this size, with numerous partners, easy implementation and handling the risks during 2020, was a great success for CESSDA and the Consortium. A Data Management Plan for the entire project was finalised, and continuous

improvements and updates were made to the SSHOC web platform resulting in access to all the available SSHOC services. Two highlights from 2020 were the successful launch of the SSHOC service catalogue and SSH Open Marketplace Consultation Platform for the tester community. Additionally, progress was made in software development and further work done on different tools and services.

Communicating and raising awareness about the SSHOC project and its results is equally important for leveraging the innovations SSHOC is introducing. The SSHOC project successfully implemented several awareness raising activities among which was co-organising the conference “REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD”, bringing together almost 700 visitors to 30 sessions and 30 virtual exhibition booths, with the goal of addressing all SSHOC stakeholders. The SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit saw the light of day and the SSHOpenMarketplace alpha and beta releases were also crucial.

The SSHOC project managed to achieve the planned results while maintaining the quality of the work. This is also supported by the positive review carried out by the European Commission. This SSHOC has established a rock-solid position for the social sciences and humanities in EOSC, which will be sustained well beyond the life of the project.

Activities and results

SSH Open Marketplace - Beta Release

- Tools & Services
- Training Materials
- Publications
- Datasets
- Workflows
- Browse
- About

Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace

Discover new resources for your research in Social Sciences and Humanities: tools, services, training materials and datasets, contextualised. Read more...

SSH Open Marketplace is under development and the current content is subject to change. Beta release is planned for December 2020.

All Categories

Content and sources

Curation and Governance

Go to the SSH Open Marketplace!

SSHOC, "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud", has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-04-2018, grant agreement #823782

- www.sshopencloud.eu
- zenodo.org/communities/sshoc
- [@SSHOpenCloud](https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud)
- [linkedin.com/company/sshoc](https://www.linkedin.com/company/sshoc)

Activities and results

ERIC Forum - ERIC Forum Implementation project

Duration: 01.01.2019 – 31.12.2022, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

The ERIC Forum Implementation project aims to strengthen the coordination within the ERIC community and enhance collaboration between partners. This is achieved through developing best practices, coordinating and sharing the necessary knowledge to support ERICs in the preparation phase, and through organising targeted thematic workshops and meetings. The project also strengthens the position of ERICs as consultation and policy stakeholders. CESSDA is one of the 23 beneficiaries of the consortium, participating in all work packages.

Updating the Forum Governance Model, ERIC Forum successfully amended the Forum's Rules of Procedure developed in 2019. ERIC Forum also supported the EC in revising the ERIC practical guidelines by collecting best practice examples from its members. Evaluation and impact assessment are critical for strengthening the ERIC community. ERIC Forum therefore collaborated with two other EU-funded projects, ACCELERATE and RI-PATHS, and organised an online workshop on "Impact Assessment, Evaluation and Monitoring of Research Infrastructures". It also established effective dialogue with the ESFRI Working Group

on monitoring and provided feedback on the early version of the Research Infrastructures' Impact Assessment Toolkit developed by the RI-PATHS project.

Lastly, ERIC Forum successfully constituted its Forward Looking Task Force in order to define the next ERIC Forum policy briefs and seminars' priorities. Its first policy brief on "Funding models for access to ERIC transnational services" was presented during the ERIC Forum Policy Seminar, virtually bringing together ERIC Forum members and key national and EU stakeholders.

TRIPLE - Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

Duration: 01.10.2019 – 31.03.2023, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

In 2020 the TRIPLE consortium successfully completed the preliminary stages of the project.

Activities and results

This was a turning point in developing the design of the platform and creating its first prototype. The heart of the Triple project is an innovative multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the social sciences and humanities (SSH). In addition, it will provide a single access point that allows researchers to explore, find, access, and reuse materials such as literature, data, projects, and researcher profiles at a European scale. The aim is to address the fragmentation of SSH research and overcome obstacles to interdisciplinary research while offering solutions for the use and reuse of SSH research.

2020 marked the preparatory stage of the project. The data acquisition model and the corresponding strategy were agreed upon. The platform's user needs were identified and feedback was provided for the design of the GOTRIPLE Platform Interface and the Trust Building System. At the same time, the development of the core TRIPLE pipeline began and possible levels of integration were discussed for GOTRIPLE and SSHOC's Open Marketplace. The specific innovative services to be integrated in the GOTRIPLE discovery platform were explored and a crowdfunding service was identified. The project investigated requirements for aligning with the EOSC, and co-organised relevant workshops and training activities with the SSHOC project.

CESSDA participates in the consortium of eighteen partners, along with its Service Providers, namely the UK Data Service (UK), FSD (FI) and ADP (SI). The contribution of CESSDA focuses on designing specifications for harvesting protocols, process, and resource metadata, as well as machine learning, open science and EOSC integration. In addition, CESSDA participates in the tasks related to outreach, training and advocacy on Open Science as well as aligning with [OPERAS](#). OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the SSH in the European Research Area.

HumMingBird - Enhanced migration measures from a multidimensional perspective

Duration: 01.12.2019 - 30.11.2023, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

The project's overall objective is to improve the understanding of the changing nature of migration flows and the drivers of migration. It will also analyse patterns, motivations, and new geographies. Moreover, HumMingBird aims to calculate population estimates, determine emerging and future trends and identify possible future implications of today's policy decisions.

Activities and results

The CESSDA team consists of CESSDA along with its Service Providers, namely EKKE (GR) and IEN (RS). A crucial task for the team is improving the Migration Data Catalogue which will feed into the CESSDA Data Catalogue. Other tasks comprise identifying migration data systems and investigating the coherence of definitions, as well as exploring links between migration policies and migration dynamics. Qualitative data will be collected from the target group and they will participate in projection estimates, while considering ethical issues.

In 2020, the project conducted a review of migration theories and a longitudinal evaluation of international migration flows. Current migration data were collected and screened while their quality and availability were assessed so that shortcomings could be identified. An expert workshop took place focusing on the gaps in migration data systems and the (missing) links with migration theories.

A Data Management Plan for the entire project was finalised and different types of data were collected. 67 sets of indicators/indexes were identified as a result of an in-depth literature review on measuring and comparing migration policies. Two of these were selected to serve the HumMingBird project. The preliminary work of depicting migrants' experiences began and the

methodology for data collection and analysis and the research strategy were developed. A communication and dissemination plan was developed and synergies were established with two sister Horizon 2020 projects. This will help project results gain visibility.

EOSC Enhance - Enhancing the EOSC portal and connecting thematic clouds

Duration: 01.12.2019 - 30.11.2021, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

EOSC Enhance's main objectives are to enhance the Service Provider interface and to accelerate the deployment and uptake of EOSC services and resources in the EOSC catalogue. As one of

the ESFRI Cluster representatives, CESSDA is principally involved in activities relating to the adaptation and further development of the EOSC catalogue. Additionally, CESSDA advises on functional specifications and tests API for interconnecting and harvesting thematic services.

A unified EOSC Interoperability Framework was developed, along with the EOSC API specifications v3.0. The end-user experience was improved through the implementation of the new Resource and Provider data model.

Participation in this project, together with the SSHOC project, has given CESSDA the opportunity to lead by onboarding SSHOC services to the EOSC portal.

EURHISFIRM - Historical high-quality company-level data for Europe

Duration: 01.04.2018 – 30.06.2021, funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

CESSDA joined EURHISFirm in 2020 in order to connect it to the SSHOC project. EURHISFIRM will design a world-class research infrastructure to collect, merge, extract, collate, align and share detailed historical high-quality company-level data for Europe. In order to achieve this goal, development of innovative tools is being carried out to spark the “Big Data” revolution in historical social sciences.

CESSDA shares its experience as a Research Infrastructure and advises about academic outputs, implementing data models and designing policies. CESSDA will enhance EURHISFIRM’s technical and scientific competencies and support the project’s research infrastructure design.

European Commission projects in the pipeline

In 2020, CESSDA was involved in the preparation and submission of several successful project proposals:

- » **COORDINATE** (INFRAIA-02, led by Manchester Metropolitan University, submitted May 2020);
- » **RITRAIN+** on training for Research Infrastructure managers (INFRA SUPP-02, led by the University of Milan-Bicocca, submitted May 2020);
- » **EOSC Future** (INFRAEOSC-03, led by the Institute for the Management of Information Systems, Athena Research Centre, submitted June 2020).

Activities and results

Technical activities

Collaboration with other infrastructures

In 2020, CESSDA continued its collaboration with infrastructures from the Social Sciences and other domains.

The [EURISE Network](#), a loose collaboration framework established with CLARIN and DARIAH, was joined by OPERAS in 2020. The planned workshop on automation and testing scheduled for March in Utrecht had to be cancelled due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead, a series of online meetings of IT experts was organised in October and November 2020.

The communication and social platform, Discord, is widely popular in computer gaming. It was used to discuss topics such as testing, automation, documentation, observability and infrastructure provisioning. There were up to 25 participants per meeting. Attendees came not only from the organising ERICs, but also from other domains with a strong and active participation from INSTRUCT ERIC. CESSDA has built on the initial collaboration with INSTRUCT beyond the technical exchange of knowledge and has plans for future joint projects.

A new Technical Committee

In the past, CESSDA's Technical Working Group focused on creating a central platform with an established design and building the individual

components that form the basis for the core products running on CESSDA's infrastructure. As the products started to become available and the platform reached a mature and stable state, the focus shifted towards service delivery.

To better reflect this operational change, the Technical Working Group concluded its work in 2020 and its advisory function to the Main Office was taken over by the new Technical Committee. The latter consists of IT experts from several Service Providers, the technical contacts. In a similar fashion, the role of content contact was created and the post-holders are attached to the Tools Working Group. All of these contact roles were awarded to Service Providers for an initial 2-year phase under an SLA (Service Level Agreement). This SLA focuses less on pre-defined outputs and instead on monitoring and steering the ongoing work relating to the services and their continued delivery.

Building on this work, CESSDA plans to continue its direction of establishing a service management system across its technical infrastructure and the services delivered by it. In the long term, CESSDA will pursue [FitSM](#) institutional certification, which is expected to become available from 2021. FitSM is a "free and lightweight standards family aimed at enabling effective IT service management in the broadest range of organisations".

Activities and results

Communications

2020 started with a face-to-face meeting of the CESSDA Communications Group in Amsterdam. This was an opportunity for communication staff from several member countries to gather over two days to work together. The first day was dedicated to getting to know each other and to developing SMART Goals for CESSDA communications and sharing aspirations. The second day was a workshop on scientific storytelling where participants got to put new techniques into practice and work together in small groups.

Then the COVID-19 pandemic struck, and all further communication activities were held online. In addition to its regular online meetings, the CESSDA Communications Group launched a new concept in 2020: tutorials. CESSDA Senior Communication Officer and a communication officer of a member archive pick a topic and organise a tutorial for the group. One tutorial was held on preparing annual reports with FORS and another on SMART (Specific Measurable Agreed Relevant Time-bound) goals for communications with NSD.

CESSDA elected a COVID-19 Ambassador, Helena Laaksonen, Director of FSD whose role was to centralise the sharing of information related to the pandemic. CESSDA worked hard to ensure that researchers could continue their work, partly thanks to the many services offered by national data archives.

Online activity

Website visits

File downloads

Twitter impressions

Top visitor countries

Top website sections

Activities and results

The CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) was increasingly populated with data sets related to the pandemic and a #COVID19data Twitter campaign was launched to promote new, relevant data sets to researchers.

CESSDA also made sure to promote the ongoing research activities of its Service Providers via a new [COVID19 web page](#). The page provides information about COVID-19 specific resources from the CESSDA consortium and other relevant sources.

This was accompanied by a new series of COVID-19 interviews targeted at researchers. Two such interviews were held in 2020 and published online:

- » [COVID-19 Interview series – Political elections](#) – Bernt Aardal, a renowned political scientist from the University of Oslo
- » [COVID-19 Interview series – CESSDA COVID-19 Ambassador](#) – Helena Laaksonen.

Website visits continued to grow in 2020 with the CESSDA website attracting over 116,000 visitors during the year. Over 73% of page views went to the training website, making it the most popular section of the website for the second year in a row.

The CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG) alone reached over 135,000 page views during the year and news items over

4,000 visits. The CESSDA Data Catalogue did remarkably well with a 62.6% increase in views with over 9,700 views in 2020 compared to just over 4,200 in 2019.

CESSDA continued its collaboration with Trust-IT services and a CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide User Story and CESSDA podcast were launched.

Four Twitter campaigns ran in 2020:

- » #COVID19data highlighting data sets in the CESSDA Data Catalogue;
- » #DMMonday (Data Management Monday) using elements from each of chapter of the CESSDA DMEG;
- » #TourofCESSDA (presenting a Service Provider);
- » #10QuestionsTo (interviewing experts).

Two articles were published in the interview series “CESSDA asks ten questions to...” (presenting ESS & EGI) and six in the “Tour of CESSDA” series (DDA, PROGEDO, FSD, APIS, FORS, NSD).

A pilot CESSDA Newsletter for Data Service Professionals was developed and sent out on average every two weeks in 2020, as part of the CESSDA Mentorship Programme ([Widening Activities & Journal Outreach 2020 Work Plan](#)). The information was mainly targeted at data service professionals, as well as data service users, namely researchers and students in the social sciences and humanities.

Activities and results

CESSDA's Senior Communication Officer developed a strategic framework for communication activities using SMART goals, based on the [AMEC Framework](#). The CESSDA AMEC Framework was reviewed every quarter with the CESSDA Director and proved a useful tool for working strategically.

An overall organisation goal as well as specific organisational and communication goals per

target audience were set for each of CESSDA's three target audiences: researchers, funders/members/policy makers, and Service Providers. The table also showed communication activities and CESSDA strove to determine the short, medium- and -long-term impacts of these activities.

Governance and management

Governance

The governance structure of CESSDA ERIC consists of the General Assembly (GA); the Director; the Service Providers and the Service Providers' Forum (SPF), which has an advisory role. The General Assembly established three advisory committees: an external Scientific Advisory Board to advise the Director, as well as a Remuneration Committee and a Strategy Committee consisting of a delegation of GA members.

The General Assembly is the ultimate authority of CESSDA ERIC and consists of the Members of CESSDA and Observers. The Director is the chief executive officer, chief scientific officer and legal representative of CESSDA.

In 2020, both the General Assembly and the Service Providers' Forum met twice, in the spring and in the autumn. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, these were virtual meetings. At the GA meetings, there were discussions on the budget, the membership fee algorithm, and on defining and collecting KPIs. CESSDA's two new members in 2020, Iceland and Ireland were also present. Externally, the focus was on EOSC and CESSDA became a member of the EOSC Association.

At the Service Provider Forum meetings, the 2019 Work Plan and ongoing work in Work Plan 2020 were reviewed along with the Agenda 21-24 and the related Consolidated

Roadmap. Advice was gathered on the 2021-2024 budget and CESSDA KPIs. CESSDA's COVID-19 Ambassador provided an update on COVID-related activities within the CESSDA community and technical group progress was also reviewed, including CESSDA services and updates to products and tools.

Management

Management of the daily operational activities of CESSDA ERIC is done by CESSDA Main Office. Its main activities are project management, communications, finance, IT-platform, acquisition and European networking and lobbying.

In 2020, CESSDA Main Office administratively managed ten internal tasks (Work Plan 2020) and six European-funded projects, including the coordination of the 14.5 million Euro SSHOC project "Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud". It also supported preparations for new applications.

In 2020, the total staff at the Main Office was 9.96 FTE; ten people in Bergen and one seconded person in Essex.

CESSDA Working Groups together with CESSDA Main Office monitored the progress and developments in each of the four strategic areas through related projects and their compliance with the CESSDA Strategy 2018-2022 and their respective Roadmaps.

Looking
Ahead

Looking ahead

The CESSDA Agenda 2020-21 is on track. We overcame the last barriers for some of the core tools, which will be operational in 2021. We managed to systematise them and secure their maintenance. Additionally, there was an upgrade of the CESSDA Data Catalogue, including back-end quality and efficiency improvements.

The KPIs for the consortium were prepared and EOSC was also established via the EOSC Association. Unfortunately, we still have to deal with COVID-19. In 2019 and 2020, we managed to transition into a phase of maturity that makes CESSDA well prepared for the next five years. We can now look forward to the deployment of the EOSC and a new Horizon Europe programme, as well as reaching full European coverage at CESSDA.

We will continue to assemble our strategy for 2022-2025 to prepare the CESSDA consortium

for the next five years. We envisage to strengthen the role and position of our Metadata Office. In addition, we plan to continue the collaboration with other science clusters.

ESFRI evaluations are approaching, and therefore EOSC and Horizon Europe will require necessary adaptations in the positioning of CESSDA within the European Research Infrastructures landscape. In addition, national states will develop their own research infrastructures, some integrating infrastructures over several domains, some combining with e-infrastructure or amalgamating with national archives and other governmental organisations.

CESSDA continues to look forward to the changes ahead, recognising an opportunity to mature further and provide valuable and exceptional services to its users.

Financial
statements

Financial statements 2020
CESSDA ERIC

Financial statements

Income statement (EUR)

Operating income and expenses	Note	2020	2019
Operating income			
Other operating income	4	1 744 630	2 262 915
Total operating income		1 744 630	2 262 915
Operating expenses			
Payroll expenses	1	864 996	933 776
Depreciation of fixed assets	2	6 518	14 297
Other operating expenses	1	798 537	1 837 243
Total operating expenses		1 670 051	2 785 317
Operating profit		74 579	-522 402
Financial income and expenses			
Other interest income		1 355	236
Other financial income		-350	24 299
Other financial expenses		-246	-33 070
Net financial income and expenses		760	-8 536
Operating result		75 339	-530 938
Annual net result		75 339	-530 938
From/ to other equity	5	75 339	-530 938
Net brought forward		75 339	-530 938

Financial statements

Balance statement (EUR)

Assets	Note	2020	2019
Tangible fixed assets			
Equipment and other movables	2	1 648	8 436
Total tangible fixed assets		1 648	8 436
Total fixed assets		1 648	8 436
Current assets			
Debtors			
Accounts receivable		-	-
Other receivables		26 960	65 182
Total debtors		26 960	65 182
Cash and bank deposits			
Cash and bank deposits	3	1 274 802	1 561 672
Total cash and bank deposits		1 274 802	1 561 672
Total current assets		1 301 762	1 626 853
Total assets		1 303 412	1 635 290

Financial statements

Balance statement (EUR)

Equity and liabilities	Note	2020	2019
Retained earnings			
Other equity	5	608 282	613 625
Total retained earnings		608 282	613 625
Total equity		608 282	613 625
Liabilities			
Trade creditors		29 989	27 091
Public duties payable		53 636	79 677
Other short term liabilities	6	611 504	914 897
Total short term liabilities		695 130	1 021 665
Total liabilities		695 130	1 021 665
Total equity and liabilities		1 303 412	1 635 290

Bergen, 6 May 2021

Ronald Jacobus Paulus Dekker
Chief Executive Officer

Accounting principles

The accounts have been prepared in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and good accounting practice in Norway. The accounting principles are described below.

As a consequence of the pandemic situation caused by COVID-19, CESSDA MO Staff have worked remotely from their home offices most of the time in year 2020. Due to travel restrictions, there has also been materially lower travel activities. Otherwise, project activities (both internal and external) have been running essentially normal.

Operating income and expenses

Revenues consist mainly of grants and project revenues. Received payments related to activities not carried out at year-end are recognised in the balance sheet as unearned income and classified as other short-term debt.

Expenses are recognised in accordance with the matching principle. This means that expenses are recognised in the same period as the related income.

Classification of assets and liabilities

Assets meant for long-term ownership or use are classified as fixed assets. Other assets are classified as current assets. Outstanding receivables to be repaid within one year are classified as current assets. The classification of liabilities is based on analogous criteria.

Fixed assets are valued at acquisition cost. Fixed assets which have a limited economic life shall be depreciated in accordance with a reasonable depreciation schedule. Fixed assets shall be written down to their fair value when a decline in value is not expected to be temporary. The write down shall be reversed when the basis for the write down is no longer present.

Current assets are valued at the lower of acquisition cost and fair value.

Liabilities are appraised at the nominal value on the acquisition date.

Taxes

Since the business is a non-profit organisation it is not liable for corporation tax in accordance with the Tax Law § 2-32.

Currency

Monetary assets and liabilities in foreign currencies are valued at the exchange rate at year-end.

Pension

The Norwegian branch has established a defined benefit pension scheme. The pension premium is classified as payroll expenses.

NOTES

Note 1- Payroll expenses, numbers of employees, loans to employees etc

Payroll expenses	2020	2019
Wages and holiday allowances	682 717	705 564
Payroll tax	99 338	126 649
Pension premium	72 269	87 176
Other benefits	10 672	14 388
Total	864 996	933 776
Average number full time equivalent	9.96	9.67
Directors' remuneration	129 046	131 844
Board fees	0	0

The company is obliged to have a pension scheme according to the Norwegian Law of compulsory occupational pension scheme and have established a defined benefit pension scheme which satisfies the requirements.

Audit Fees	2020	2019
Audit	3 788	7 299
Other services		1 541
Total	3 788	8 840

Audit costs are exclusive value added tax.

Note 2 - Tangible fixed assets

Assets	2020	2019
Acquisition cost 01.01	67 808	60 828
Acquisition	0	6 980
Acquisition cost 31.12	67 808	67 808
Accumulated depreciation	-66 161	-59 372
Accounted value	1 648	8 436
Depreciation of the year	6 518	14 297
Expected economic life	3-5 years	3-5 years
Deprecation plan	Linear	Linear

Note 3 - Cash and bank deposits

The bank deposits includes EUR 29 114 of tax deduction funds.

Deposit	2020	2019
Restricted cash- employee tax deduction funds	29 114	39 941
Bank deposits in NOK	124 366	2 130
Bank deposits in EUR	1 121 322	1 519 601
Total	1 274 803	1 561 673

Cessda ERIC has a currency risk associated with the exchange rate developments. Allocated funding to projects are paid in Euros. The bank deposits are in Norwegian Kroner and Euro.

Note 4 - Breakdown of income

Income in the year was derived from the following sources:

	2020	2019
Members' contributions	1 511 365	1 920 954
Other Grant income	233 265	341 961
Total	1 744 630	2 262 915

Note 5 - Changes in equity

Prefundings received by the EC and which relates to the following year(s) have been excluded from the income and treated as deferred income.

Equity	2020	2019
Equity 01.01	613 624	1 119 096
Reporting currency EUR	-80 688	0
Translation difference, change in reporting currency	7	25 466
Result of the year	75 339	-530 938
Total equity 31.12	608 282	613 624

Note 6 - Other short term liabilities

Liability	2020	2019
WPT; funds granted to projects, not paid as of 31.12	166 573	811 524
EC projects; funds granted to projects, not paid as of 31.12	287 291	23 774
EC projects; prefinancing, received as at 31.12	81 955	
Other short term liabilities	159 311	79 600
Total other short term liabilities per 31.12	695 130	914 897

Projects that have been granted funds from CESSDA ERIC, where payments has not taken place at year-end, is classified as other short term liabilities. As of 31 December this amounts to EUR 166.573.

BDO AS
Inger Bang Lunds vei 4
5059 Bergen

Independent Auditor's Report

To the General Meeting in CESSDA ERIC

Report on the Audit of the Financial Statements

Opinion

We have audited the financial statements of CESSDA ERIC.

<p>The financial statements comprise:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• The balance sheet as at 31 December 2020• The income statement for 2020• Notes to the financial statements, including a summary of significant accounting policies	<p>In our opinion:</p> <p>The accompanying financial statements are prepared in accordance with the law and regulations and give a true and fair view of the financial position of the Company as at 31 December 2020 and its financial performance for the year then ended in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and accounting standards and practices generally accepted in Norway.</p>
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Basis for Opinion

We conducted our audit in accordance with laws, regulations, and auditing standards and practices generally accepted in Norway, including International Standards on Auditing (ISAs). Our responsibilities under those standards are further described in the Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements section of our report. We are independent of the Company as required by laws and regulations, and we have fulfilled our other ethical responsibilities in accordance with these requirements. We believe that the audit evidence we have obtained is sufficient and appropriate to provide a basis for our opinion.

The responsibilities of the Managing Director for the Financial Statements

The Managing Director (management) is responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of the financial statements in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and accounting standards and practices generally accepted in Norway, and for such internal control as management determines is necessary to enable the preparation of financial statements that are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error.

In preparing the financial statements, management is responsible for assessing the Company's ability to continue as a going concern, disclosing, as applicable, matters related to going concern. The financial statements use the going concern basis of accounting insofar as it is not likely that the enterprise will cease operations.

Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements

Our objectives are to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements as a whole are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error, and to issue an auditor's report that includes our opinion. Reasonable assurance is a high level of assurance, but is not a guarantee that an audit conducted in accordance with ISAs will always detect a material

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misstatement when it exists. Misstatements can arise from fraud or error and are considered material if, individually or in the aggregate, they could reasonably be expected to influence the economic decisions of users taken on the basis of these financial statements.

For further description of Auditor's Responsibilities for the Audit of the Financial Statements reference is made to:

<https://revisorforeningen.no/revisjonsberetninger>

Report on Other Legal and Regulatory Requirements

Opinion on Registration and Documentation

Based on our audit of the financial statements as described above, and control procedures we have considered necessary in accordance with the International Standard on Assurance Engagements (ISAE) 3000, «Assurance Engagements Other than Audits or Reviews of Historical Financial Information», it is our opinion that management has fulfilled its duty to produce a proper and clearly set out registration and documentation of the company's accounting information in accordance with the law and bookkeeping standards and practices generally accepted in Norway.

BDO AS

Charlotte Bårdsen
State Authorised Public Accountant
(This document is signed electronically)

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Annex

CESSDA ERIC Members / Observers and Service Providers 2020

Country	Representing entity	Service Provider	GA Delegates	SPF Delegates
Austria	BMBWF - Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)	AUSSDA - The Austrian Social Science Data Archive	Matthias Reiter- Pázmándy, BMBWF Bettina Glazer, BMBWF (deputy) - Lars Kaczmirek, AUSSDA Lisa Hönegger, AUSSDA	Lars Kaczmirek Lisa Hönegger
Belgium	BELSPO - Belgian Scientific Policy Office	SOHDA - Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive	Laurence Lenoir, BELSPO Aziz Naji, BELSPO	Benjamin Peuch Laura Van Den Borre
Croatia	Ministry of Science and Education	Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb	Slaven Mihaljević, Ministry	Marijana Glavica
Czech Republic	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports	CSDA - the Czech Social Science Data Archive	Kamila Gabrielova, Ministry Jindrich Krejci, CSDA	Jindrich Krejci Yana Leontiyeva
Denmark	Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education	DNA - Danish Data Archive	Katinka Stenbjørn, Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education (until June 2020) Kirsten Villadsen Kristmar, DNA	Anne Sofie Fink

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Finland	Academy of Finland	FSD - Finnish Social Science Data Archive	Vilma Lehtinen, Academy of Finland Helena Laaksonen, FSD	Helena Laaksonen
France	Ministry of Education, Higher Education and Research	PROGEDO/CNRS	Fabrice Boudjaaba, CNRS Basudeb Chaudhuri, Ministry	Sebastien Oliveau
Germany	BMBF - Federal Ministry of Education and Research	GESIS	Miriam Schriefers, Ministry Alexia Katsanidou, GESIS	Libby Bishop Alexia Katsanidou
Greece	So.Da.Net - Greek research infrastructure for the social sciences	So.Da.Net	John Kallas Dimitra Kondyli	Dimitra Kondyli
Hungary	NRDI - The National Research, Development and Innovation Office	TÁRKI Foundation	Gábor Csirikusz, NRDI Bela Janky, TÁRKI	Peter Hegedus Bela Junky
Iceland	Ministry of Education, Science and Culture of Iceland	DATICE - Social Science Research Institute	Guðbjörg Andrea Jónsdóttir, DATICE	Guðbjörg Andrea Jónsdóttir Örnólfur Thorlacius
Ireland	Irish Research Council	ISSDA - Irish Social Science Data Archive	Peter Brown, Irish Research Council, Director Rosemary Sweeney, Irish Research Council	John Howard Julia Barrett

Netherlands	NWO - Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	DANS - Data Archiving and Networked Services	Joris Voskuilen, NWO Peter Doorn, DANS	Ricarda Braukmann Ingrid Dillo
North Macedonia	Ministry of Education and Science	SS Cyril and Methodius University	Klime Babunski Andrea Aleksovski, Ministry	Aneta Cekikj
Norway	Research Council of Norway	NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data	Bjørn Tore Kjellemo, Research Council (until June 2020) Siri Lader Bruhn (from June 2020) Vigdis Kvalheim, NSD	Vigdis Kvalheim Dag Kiberg
Portugal	Institute of Social Science, University of Lisbon	APIS - Portuguese Archive of Social Information	Pedro Moura Ferreira, University of Lisbon Jose Manuel Mendes, University of Coimbria	Pedro Moura Ferreira Jose Manuel Mendes
Serbia	Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development	SER.DAC - Serbian Data Centre in Social Sciences	Aleksandra Bradic- Martinovic, SER.DAC Marija Kuzmanovic, Ministry	Aleksandra Bradic- Martinovic
Slovakia	Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic (Expert: Institute for Sociology of Slovak Academy of Sciences)	SASD - Slovak Archive of Social Data	Miloslav Bahna, Institute for Sociology of Slovak Academy of Sciences	Miloslav Bahna Katarina Strapcova

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Slovenia	MIZs - Ministry of Education, Science and Sport	ADP - Social Science Data Archives	Albin Kral, MIZs Janez Stebe, ADP	Janez Stebe Irena Vipavc Brvar
Sweden	Swedish Research Council	SND - Swedish National Data Service	Mikael Hjerm, Umeå University Magnus Eriksson, Research Council	Iris Alfredsson Max Petzold
Switzerland	FORS - The Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences	FORS	Georg Lutz, FORS Brian Kleiner, FORS	Brian Kleiner Alexandra Stam
United Kingdom	BEIS - Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy	UKDS - UK Data Service	Carlos Pueyo Recio-Mensaquel, BEIS (until October 2020) Kieran Jarrett, BEIS (from October 2020) Matthew Woollard, UKDS	Herve L'Hours Matthew Woollard

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